

Guide to Case Law

MOTHER EARTH MSCA POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP

Alice Lopes Fabris.

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Introduction

This booklet is a part of a toolkit developed in the framework of the MSCA Project Mother Earth: Mother Earth: The Impact of Human-Induced Environmental Degradation on the Cultural Rights of Indigenous and Afro-Indigenous Peoples.

It provides examples of case law relating to the impact of environmental degradation on the rights of indigenous peoples and Afro-descendant communities, particularly with regard to their cultural rights. It comprises decisions issued by various international bodies, including the Inter-American Court of Human Rights, the UN Human Rights Committee (CCPR), the UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR), the Committee on the Rights of the Child (CRC), the Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD) and the International Labour Organization (ILO).

The guide aims to provide lawyers, communities, and other stakeholders with examples of decisions that could help them secure the rights of Indigenous peoples and Afro-descendant communities. Highlighting these cases enables communities, advocates and organisations to gain a better understanding of how international law can support their efforts to protect their territories, communities and ways of life.

Methodology

This guide adopts a systematic approach to identifying and selecting cases concerning the rights of Indigenous Peoples and Afro-Descendant Communities within three major human rights systems: the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR), the International Labour Organisation (ILO), and the United Nations (UN). The methodologies applied to each institution were designed to ensure the inclusion of cases providing substantive legal reasoning and guidance on collective rights, cultural integrity, and the protection of ancestral lands.

Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR)

The methodology for identifying relevant IACtHR caselaw on the rights of Indigenous Peoples and Afro-descendant Communities involved a two-stage process using the Court's official database. First, the list of IACtHR decisions from the Rapporteurship on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples was consulted, providing a comprehensive record of relevant cases up to 2018. Secondly, a manual review was conducted of all IACtHR judgements from 2018 onwards to identify additional cases addressing the rights of indigenous peoples and Afro-descendant communities.

Methodology

United Nations (UN) Treaty Bodies

To identify relevant UN jurisprudence, a search was conducted in October 2024 using the OHCHR Jurisprudence Database, with the keywords “indigenous” and “tribal”. The search yielded 70 results, which were then manually screened to ensure that only cases with substantial legal reasoning concerning the application of right to culture and protection of the environment were retained. Cases from the Committee Against Torture were excluded to maintain a thematic focus. Cases addressing broader population groups without distinguishing Indigenous Peoples as a distinct legal category were also excluded. Cases concerning political rights, fair trial, and procedure rights were also excluded.

International Labour Organisation (ILO)

A targeted search within the ILO database was conducted to identify cases in which either Convention No. 107 or No. 169 was directly applied, interpreted or discussed. This process yielded a focused body of jurisprudence addressing the protection and promotion of the rights of indigenous and tribal peoples in the context of labour, land, and consultation. All cases are listed in this guide.

Inter-American Court of Human Rights

(IACtHR)

IACtHR

The Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR) plays a fundamental role in protecting and promoting human rights across the Americas.

Established in 1979, the Court is an autonomous judicial institution of the Organisation of American States (OAS), responsible for interpreting and enforcing the American Convention on Human Rights (ACHR), as well as other regional human rights instruments.

Through its jurisprudence, the IACtHR has developed a rich body of case law that addresses not only individual violations, but also sets binding standards for states to ensure the full realisation of human rights, including the rights of indigenous peoples and Afro-descendant communities.

This section presents a selection of judgments and advisory opinions from the IACtHR that demonstrate how it has interpreted the rights of indigenous peoples and afro-descendant communities over time.

List of cases

The Mayagna (Sumo) Awas Tingni Community v. Nicaragua
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U'wa Indigenous People and its members v. Colombia
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Advisory Opinion AO-32/25 Climate Emergency and Human Rights

The Mayagna (Sumo) Awas Tingni Community v. Nicaragua

Judgment of Preliminary Objections. on
1st February 2000. Series C No. 66.

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and Costs
on 31st August 2001. Series C No. 79.

This case concerned the State's failure to recognise, define and protect the **collective property rights** of the Awas Tingni indigenous community over its ancestral lands and natural resources.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to respect rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to adopt domestic legal provisions)
- Article 4 (Right to life)
- Article 11 (Right to honour and dignity)
- Article 12 (Freedom of conscience and religion)
- Article 16 (Right to freedom of association)
- Article 21 (Right to private property)
- Article 22 (Right of movement and residence)
- Article 23 (Political rights)
- Article 25 (Judicial protection)

Moiwana Community v. Suriname

Judgment of Preliminary Objections,
Merits, Reparations and Costs on 15 June
2005. Series C No. 124.

This case concerned the massacre of the Moiwana Maroon community in Suriname on 29 November 1986. The attack was carried out by state security forces, resulting in the deaths of more than 40 men, women and children, as well as the destruction of their village. The survivors were forced to flee, which led to exile and internal displacement and prevented them from returning to their traditional lands and way of life.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to respect rights)
- Article 5 (Right to personal integrity)
- Article 8 (Judicial guarantees)
- Article 21 (Right to private property)
- Article 22 (Right of movement and residence)
- Article 25 (Judicial protection)

Yakye Axa Indigenous Community v. Paraguay

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and
Costs on 17 June 2005. Series C No. 125.

This case concerned the State's failure to guarantee the Yakye Axa Indigenous Community's ancestral property rights in Paraguay. The community's land claim has remained unresolved since 1993, preventing its members from owning and occupying their traditional territory.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to respect rights)
- Article 2 (Duty to adopt domestic legal provisions)
- Article 4 (Right to life)
- Article 5 (Right to personal integrity)
- Article 7 (Right to personal liberty)
- Article 8 (Judicial guarantees)
- Article 19 (Rights of the child)
- Article 21 (Right to private property)
- Article 25 (Judicial protection)

Sawhoyamaya Indigenous Community v. Paraguay

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and
Costs on 29 March 2006. Series C No. 146.

This case concerned the state's failure to recognise and guarantee the ancestral property rights of the Sawhoyamaya indigenous community in Paraguay. The community's claim to title and possession of their traditional lands has remained unresolved since 1991, leaving them without access to their territory and in a state of extreme vulnerability.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to respect rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to adopt domestic legal provisions)
- Article 3 (Right to recognition as a person before the law)
- Article 4 (Right to life)
- Article 8 (Judicial Guarantees)
- Article 19 (Rights of the child)
- Article 21 (Right to private property)
- Article 25 (Judicial protection)

Saramaka People v. Suriname

Judgment of Preliminary Objections,
Merits, Reparations, and Costs on 28
November 2007. Series C No. 172.

This case concerns the violation of the Saramaka people's collective land and resource rights. The Saramaka people are a tribal community living in the Upper Suriname River region. The state granted logging and mining concessions within the Saramaka people's ancestral territory without prior consultation.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to respect rights)
- Article 2 (Duty to adopt domestic legal provisions)
- Article 3 (Right to recognition as a person before the law)
- Article 21 (Right to private property)
- Article 25 (Judicial protection)

Xákmok Kásek Indigenous Community. v. Paraguay

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and Costs
on 24 August 2010. Series C No. 214.

This case concerns the state's failure to guarantee the ancestral land rights of the Xákmok Kásek indigenous community and its members. Despite the community's land claim having been pending since 1990, the state has failed to provide a satisfactory resolution, thereby preventing the community from accessing and possessing its traditional lands.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to respect rights)
- Article 2 (Duty to adopt domestic legal provisions)
- Article 3 (Right to recognition as a person before the law)
- Article 4 (Right to life)
- Article 5 (Right to personal integrity)
- Article 8 (Judicial guarantees)
- Article 19 (Rights of the child)
- Article 21 (Right to private property)
- Article 25 (Judicial protection)

Kichwa Indigenous People of Sarayaku v. Ecuador

Judgment of Merits and Reparations on
27 June 2012. Series C No. 245.

This case concerns the state's failure to consult with or obtain the consent of the Sarayaku Kichwa indigenous people before granting a private oil company permission to explore for and exploit oil on their ancestral territory.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to respect rights)
- Article 4 (Right to Life)
- Article 5 (Right to Personal Integrity)
- Article 7 (Right to Personal Freedom)
- Article 8 (Judicial Guarantees)
- Article 13 (Freedom of thought and expression)
- Article 21 (Right to private property)
- Article 22 (Right of movement and residence)
- Article 23 (Political rights)
- Article 25 (Judicial Protection)
- Article 26 (Progressive Development)

Afro-Descendant Communities Displaced from the Cacarica River Basin (Operation Genesis) v. Colombia

Judgment of Preliminary Objections,
Merits, Reparations and Costs on 20
November 2013. Series C No. 270.

This case concerns Operation Genesis, a counterinsurgency operation that took place from 24 to 27 February 1997 in the territories of Afro-descendant communities in the Cacarica River Basin. The State allegedly violated the communities' collective property rights by allowing and tolerating their forced displacement, as well as the illegal exploitation of natural resources by companies.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 4 (Right to Life)
- Article 5 (Right to Humane Treatment)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 19 (Rights of the Child)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 22 (Freedom of Movement and Residence)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)

Kuna Indigenous People of Madungandí and the Emberá Indigenous People of Bayano and their Members v. Panama

Judgment of Preliminary Objections,
Merits, Reparations and Costs on 14
October 2014. Series C No. 284.

This case concerns the construction of a hydroelectric dam in 1972 on the lands of the Kuna indigenous community of Madungandí and the Emberá indigenous community of Bayano.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to respect rights)
- Article 2 (Duty to adopt domestic legal provisions)
- Article 8 (Judicial guarantees)
- Article 21 (Right to private property)
- Article 25 (Judicial protection)

Garífuna Triunfo de la Cruz Community and its Members v. Honduras

Judgment of Preliminary Objections,
Merits, Reparations and Costs on 8
October 2015. Series C No. 305.

This case concerns the Garífuna Triunfo de la Cruz community, an indigenous, rural community in Honduras. Although the state granted the community ownership of various parcels of its ancestral lands between the 1940s and 2000s, it allowed urban expansion and transferred land for industrial and tourism purposes. It also created a protected national park on the community's territory.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)

Garífuna Punta Piedra Community and its Members v. Honduras

Judgment of Preliminary Objections,
Merits, Reparations and Costs on 8
October 2015. Series C No. 304.

This case concerns the Garífuna Punta Piedra community, an indigenous group in Honduras. Although the community was granted ownership of part of its collective farming area in 1920, this did not encompass all of its ancestral lands. In the 1990s, the community sought recognition of its remaining ancestral lands. However, the state allocated some of these lands to third parties through a 2001 agreement, failing to fulfil all its obligations under the agreement.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)

Kaliña and Lokono Peoples v. Suriname

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and Costs on 25 November 2015. Series C No. 309.

This case concerns the indigenous Kaliña and Lokono peoples of Suriname. Between the 1960s and 1980s, the state established three nature reserves on their ancestral territory, restricting their access to parts of it. The state also permitted mining in these reserves, causing severe ecological damage, and sold neighbouring land to non-indigenous parties for urban development.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 3 (Right to Juridical Personality)
- Article 13 (Freedom of Thought and Expression)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)

Xucuru Indigenous People and its Members v. Brazil

Judgement of Preliminary Objections,
Merits, Reparations and Costs. on 5
February 2017. Series C No. 346.

This case concerns the Xucuru indigenous community in the Brazilian state of Pernambuco. The case addresses the recognition, classification, demarcation and definition of their ancestral lands.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and
Costs on 6 February 2020.

Series C No. 400.

Indigenous Communities of the Lhaka Honhat Association (Our Land) v. Argentina

This case concerns the Lhaka Honhat indigenous communities in the province of Salta, Argentina, and their long-standing struggle to obtain recognition of, and protection for, their ancestral lands.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)
- Article 26 (Progressive Development)

Maya Kaqchikel Indigenous Peoples of Sumpango et al v. Guatemala

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and
Costs on 16 May 2023. Series C No. 488.

This case concerns the Maya Q'eqchi' Agua Caliente indigenous community in Guatemala and the state's responsibility for violating their collective and individual rights. The case relates to the lack of domestic legislation protecting the community's collective property rights, the granting of a mining project on their ancestral lands without consultation or consent, and the absence of effective legal remedies to safeguard these rights.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 3 (Right to Juridical Personality)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 13 (Freedom of Thought and Expression)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and
Costs on 16 May 2023. Series C No. 488.

Maya Q'eqchi' Indigenous Community of Agua Caliente v. Guatemala

This case concerns the Agua Caliente Maya Q'eqchi' Indigenous Community's request for recognition of their collective land rights and related rights to natural resources in Guatemala.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 4 (Right to Life)
- Article 5 (Right to Humane Treatment)
- Article 13 (Freedom of Thought and Expression)
- Article 19 (Rights of the Child)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 26 (Progressive Development/Healthy Environment)

La Oroya Population v. Peru

Judgment of Preliminary Objections,
Merits, Reparations and Costs on 27
November 2023. Series C No. 511.

This case concerns the Oroya population in Peru and their claim for protection of the right to a healthy environment in the context of mining activities.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 4 (Right to Life)
- Article 5 (Right to Humane Treatment)
- Article 13 (Freedom of Thought and Expression)
- Article 19 (Rights of the Child)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 26 (Progressive Development/Healthy Environment)

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and Costs on 1st April 2024. Series C No. 522.

Rama and Kriol Peoples, the Black Creole Indigenous Community of Bluefields et al. v. Nicaragua

This case concerns the property rights of the Rama and Kriol peoples of Nicaragua.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 24 (Right to Equal Protection)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)
- Article 26 (Progressive Development/Healthy Environment)

U'wa Indigenous People and its members v. Colombia

Judgment of Merits, Reparations and
Costs on 4 July 2024. Series C No. 530.

This case concerns the collective property rights of the U'wa indigenous people of Colombia. The violations stem from a lack of comprehensive land titling, as well as the implementation of oil, mining, tourism and infrastructure projects on their ancestral territory without prior consultation.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 13 (Freedom of Thought and Expression)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)
- Article 26 (Progressive Development/Healthy Environment)

Judgment of Preliminary Objection,
Merits, Reparations and Costs on 4
September 2024. Series C No. 537.

Tagaeri and Taromenane Indigenous Peoples v. Ecuador

This case concerns the Tagaeri and Taromenane indigenous peoples of Ecuador, who live in voluntary isolation. The case discussed violations that occurred in the context of projects affecting their territories, natural resources and traditional way of life.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 4 (Right to Life)
- Article 5 (Right to Humane Treatment)
- Article 7 (Right to Personal Liberty)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 11 (Right to Privacy)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)
- Article 26 (Progressive Development/Healthy Environment)

Advisory Opinion AO- 32/25 Climate Emergency and Human Rights

Advisory Opinion AO-32/25
of 29 May 2025.

This case concerns an advisory opinion request submitted on 9 January 2023 by the Republic of Chile and the Republic of Colombia to the Inter-American Court of Human Rights. The request seeks clarification on state obligations in addressing the climate emergency within the framework of international human rights law.

Articles discussed in the case:

- Article 1 (Obligation to Respect Rights)
- Article 2 (Obligation to Give Domestic Legal Effect to Rights)
- Article 4 (Right to Life)
- Article 5 (Right to Humane Treatment)
- Article 8 (Right to a Fair Trial)
- Article 11 (Right to Privacy)
- Article 13 (Freedom of Thought and Expression)
- Article 17 (Rights of the Family)
- Article 19 (Rights of the Child)
- Article 21 (Right to Property)
- Article 22 (Freedom of Movement and Residence)
- Article 23 (Right to Participate in Government)
- Article 25 (Right to Judicial Protection)

Human Rights Committee

(CCPR)

UN Human Rights Committee (CCPR)

The Human Rights Committee (CCPR) is a group of independent experts who monitor how countries implement the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR).

This caselaw guide focuses on the application of Article 27 of the ICCPR, which states that:

“In those States in which ethnic, religious or linguistic minorities exist, persons belonging to such minorities shall not be denied the right, in community with the other members of their group, **to enjoy their own culture**, to profess and practise their own religion, or to use their own language.”

Ominayak (Lubicon Lake Band) v. Canada

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/38/D/167/1984

Communication number: 167/1984

Author: Bernard Ominayak,

Chief of the Lubicon Lake Band

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Session No: 38

Country: Canada

Date of the decision: 26 Mar 1990

The Lubicon Lake Band, an Indigenous People in Canada, claimed that the government violated their right to self-determination by allowing the province of Alberta to give away their traditional lands for oil and gas exploration.

Claim: They argued that this development destroyed their environment, damaged their economic base, and threatened their ability to live according to their traditional way of life, even though their rights had been recognised in Treaty 8 (1899) and the Indian Act (1970).

The community said these actions deprived them of their lands, natural resources, and means of subsistence, violating their right to freely determine their political, economic, social, and cultural future under Article 1 of the Covenant.

While the claim was presented under Article 1, the Human Rights Committee noted that the facts could also raise issues under other articles of the Covenant, including Article 27. The Committee therefore decided to examine these issues further to determine whether any violations of Article 27 or other rights had occurred.

Ominayak (Lubicon Lake Band) v. Canada

The Committee has stated that:

“Although initially couched in terms of alleged breaches of the provisions of article 1 of the Covenant, there is no doubt that many of the claims presented raise issues under article 27. The Committee recognizes that the rights protected by article 27, include the right of persons, in community with others, to engage in economic and social activities which are part of the culture of the community to which they belong.” (para. 32.2)

Pereira and the other members of the Campo Agua' indigenous community v. Paraguay

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/132/D/2552/2015

Communication number: 2552/2015

Author: Benito Oliveira Pereira and

Lucio Guillermo Sosa Benega

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Session No: 132

Country: Paraguay

Date of the decision: 14 Jul 2021

The authors claimed that aerial fumigation in their territory violated their community's rights under Article 27 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, which protects the right to enjoy one's culture.

Claim: They explained that the fumigation destroyed biodiversity and natural resources essential to their cultural identity and traditional way of life. The loss of plants, animals, and forest materials made it impossible to continue important cultural and spiritual practices, such as hunting, fishing, and traditional ceremonies like the mitãkarai (baptism ritual).

The community also argued that they were not consulted before the fumigation, which ignored their right to free, prior, and informed consent. As a result, they suffered environmental damage, food scarcity, and cultural loss, forcing some families to leave their territory and threatening the survival of their cultural identity.

Pereira and the other members of the Campo Agua' indigenous community v. Paraguay

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee recalls that, in the case of indigenous peoples, the enjoyment of culture may relate to a way of life which is closely associated with territory and the use of its resources, including such traditional activities as fishing or hunting. Thus, the protection of this right is directed towards ensuring the survival and continued development of the cultural identity.” (para. 8.6)

“The Committee finds that article 27, interpreted in the light of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, enshrines the inalienable right of indigenous peoples to enjoy the territories and natural resources that they have traditionally used for their subsistence and cultural identity.” (para. 8.6)

Pereira and the other members of the Campo Agua' indigenous community v. Paraguay

The Committee has stated that:

“In the present case, the Committee notes that the authors and other members of the community exercise the right to enjoy their culture through a way of life that is closely linked with their territory and the use of the natural resources found therein. The Committee also notes that the large-scale fumigation with toxic agrochemicals presents a threat which the State party could reasonably have foreseen. Not only were the competent State authorities notified of the activities and their impact on the community members, but the prosecutor’s office found that the acts fully met the definition of the offence (...) and the accused themselves acknowledged their liability (...). Yet, the State party did not put a stop to the activities, thus allowing the continued contamination of the rivers in which the authors fish, draw their water, bathe and wash their clothing, the further death of their livestock, a source of food, and the ongoing destruction of their crops and the resources in the forest where they forage and hunt. The Committee further notes that the State party has not provided an alternative explanation of what happened or demonstrated having taken any steps whatsoever to protect the right of the authors and other community members to their cultural life. The Committee accordingly finds that the facts before it disclose a violation of article 27 of the Covenant with regard to the Campo Agua’ indigenous community.” (para. 8.8)

Poma Poma v. Peru

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/95/D/1457/2006

Communication number: 1457/2006

Author: Ángela Poma Poma

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Session No: 95

Country: Peru

Date of the decision: 27 Mar 2009

The author, a member of an Aymara Indigenous community, claimed that the diversion of groundwater from her people's land destroyed the local ecosystem of the altiplano, dried up wetlands, and caused the death of thousands of llamas and alpacas, their main source of food and income.

She argued that this environmental destruction deprived the community of its traditional way of life, which depends on raising livestock and living from the land.

Violation to the Article 27 were not argued by the claimant, but the Committee has understood that the grievences raised in the application concerned Article 27, and has held the petition admissible under this Article.

Poma Poma v. Peru

The Committee has stated that:

“In previous cases, the Committee has recognized that the rights protected by article 27 include the right of persons, in community with others, to engage in economic and social activities which are part of the culture of the community to which they belong.

In the present case, it is undisputed that the author is a member of an ethnic minority and that raising llamas is an essential element of the culture of the Aymara community, since it is a form of subsistence and an ancestral tradition handed down from parent to child.” (para. 7.3)

“The Committee also observes that the author has been unable to continue benefiting from her traditional economic activity owing to the drying out of the land and loss of her livestock.

The Committee therefore considers that the State’s action has substantively compromised the way of life and culture of the author, as a member of her community. The Committee concludes that the activities carried out by the State party violate the right of the author to enjoy her own culture together with the other members of her group, in accordance with article 27 of the Covenant.” (para. 7.7)

Billy and others v. Australia

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/135/D/3624/2019

Communication number: 3624/2019

Author: Daniel Billy and others

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Session No: 135

Country: Australia

Date of the decision: 21 Jul 2022

The authors claimed that climate change is threatening their traditional way of life and cultural survival, in violation of Article 27 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

They explained that their culture depends on their islands and the surrounding seas, which are being damaged by rising sea levels and other effects of climate change. As their islands become less habitable, they risk being displaced from their ancestral lands, which would cause serious and irreversible harm to their ability to practice and enjoy their culture.

Billy and others v. Australia

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee also recalls that, in the case of Indigenous Peoples, the enjoyment of culture may relate to a way of life which is closely associated with territory and the use of its resources, including such traditional activities as fishing or hunting. Thus, the protection of this right is directed towards ensuring the survival and continued development of cultural identity.” (para. 8.13)

“The Committee further recalls that article 27 of the Covenant, interpreted in the light of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, enshrines the inalienable right of Indigenous Peoples to enjoy the territories and natural resources that they have traditionally used for their subsistence and cultural identity. Although the rights protected under article 27 are individual rights, they depend in turn on the ability of the minority group to maintain its culture, language or religion.” (para. 8.13)

Billy and others v. Australia

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee considers that the climate impacts mentioned by the authors represent a threat that could have reasonably been foreseen by the State party, as the authors’ community members began raising the issue in the 1990s. While noting the completed and ongoing sea wall construction on the islands where the authors live, the Committee considers that the delay in initiating these projects indicates an inadequate response by the State party to the threat faced by the authors. (...) The Committee considers that the information made available to it indicates that the State party’s failure to adopt timely adequate adaptation measures to protect the authors’ collective ability to maintain their traditional way of life and to transmit to their children and future generations their culture and traditions and use of land and sea resources discloses a violation of the State party’s positive obligation to protect the authors’ right to enjoy their minority culture. Accordingly, the Committee considers that the facts before it amount to a violation of the authors’ rights under article 27 of the Covenant.” (para. 8.14)

Ailsa Roy v. Australia

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/137/D/3585/2019

Communication number: 3585/2019

Author: Ailsa Roy

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Session No: 137

Country: Australia

Date of the decision: 13 March 2024

The author claimed that the Wunna Nyiyaparli people were denied their right to effectively participate in court proceedings that decided ownership of their traditional lands. The land was granted to another Indigenous group, mainly due to interests in mining concessions.

She argued that this lack of participation led to the loss of their ancestral territory, which is at the heart of their culture, laws, and customs. Without their land, their way of life and cultural identity as the Wunna Nyiyaparli people are at risk of disappearing, a violation of their right to enjoy their culture in community with others under Article 27 of the Covenant.

Ailsa Roy v. Australia

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee recalls that ancestral cemeteries, places of religious meaning and importance and ceremonial or ritual sites linked to the occupation and use of physical territories constitute an intrinsic part of the right to cultural identity; therefore, limitations on the right to traditional territories can also affect the right to the exercise of religion, spirituality or beliefs.” (para. 8.4)

“The Committee recalls that article 27 of the Covenant enshrines the inalienable right of Indigenous Peoples to enjoy their traditional territories and that any decision affecting them should be taken with their effective participation.” (para. 8.6)

Ailsa Roy v. Australia

The Committee has stated that:

“In the present case, the Committee notes that, beyond indicating that the Federal Court did not consider the Wunna Nyiyaparli to be Nyiyaparli Indigenous Peoples, the State party does not contest their self-identification as Indigenous Peoples. The State party also does not contest that they maintain cultural interests in the territory that they have used and occupied for immemorial time, known as the Roy Hill Pastoral Lease, which holds their sacred sites and is key to their language, culture, religion and preservation as an Indigenous People as such. Nevertheless, the Committee notes that the State party has not demonstrated having taken any steps to protect the right of the Wunna Nyiyaparli to enjoy their culture, having on the contrary attributed their traditional territory to another Indigenous group without having ensured their effective participation in the proceedings for the determination of their fundamental right to traditional territory, a decision affecting their survival as a people. In the light of the foregoing, the Committee concludes that the facts before it disclose a violation of article 27 of the Covenant, read in the light of article 1 of the Covenant and of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.” (para. 8.7)

Mahuika et al. v. New Zealand

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/70/D/547/1993

Communication number: 547/1993

Author: Apirana Mahuika et al.

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Session No: 70

Country: New Zealand

Date of the decision: 27 Oct 2000

The authors of this claim argued that the Treaty of Waitangi (Fisheries Claims) Settlement Act 1992 took away their traditional fishing rights and threatened their cultural survival. They claimed that fishing is a central part of their culture and way of life, and that the government's actions violated their right, under Article 27 of the ICCPR, to enjoy and practice their culture.

The Committee has stated that:

“The right to enjoy one's culture cannot be determined in abstracto but has to be placed in context. In particular, article 27 does not only protect traditional means of livelihood of minorities, but allows also for adaptation of those means to the modern way of life and ensuing technology.” (para. 9.4)

“The Committee recalls its general comment on article 27, according to which, especially in the case of indigenous peoples, the enjoyment of the right to one's own culture may require positive legal measures of protection by a State party and measures to ensure the effective participation of members of minority communities in decisions which affect them.” (para. 9.5)

Howard v. Canada

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/84/D/879/1999
Communication number: 879/1999
Author: George Howard
Type of decision: Decision on merits
Session No: 84
Country: Canada
Date of the decision: 26 Jul 2005

The author claimed that he and other members of his First Nation were being denied the right to practice their traditional fishing activities, both individually and as a community. He argued that this violated Article 27 of the ICCPR.

It was explained that hunting, fishing, gathering, and trapping are essential parts of his people's cultural, spiritual, and social life, and that losing these practices would threaten their cultural survival and their ability to pass traditions to future generations.

“The Committee considers that it is not in a position to draw independent conclusions on the factual circumstances in which the author can exercise his right to fish and their consequences for his enjoyment of the right to his own culture. While the Committee understands the author's concerns, especially bearing in mind the relatively small size of the reserves in question and the limitations imposed on fishing outside the reserves, and without prejudice to any legal proceedings or negotiations between the Williams Treaties First Nations and the Government, the Committee is of the opinion that the information before it is not sufficient to justify the finding of a violation of article 27 of the Covenant.” (para. 2.11)

Äärelä and Näkkäljärvi v. Finland

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/73/D/779/1997

Communication number: 779/1997

Author: Anni Äärelä and Jouni Näkkäljärvi

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Session No: 73

Country: Finland

Date of the decision: 24 Oct 2001

The authors claimed that their right to enjoy their culture, protected under Article 27 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, was violated when the authorities allowed logging and road construction in the Kariselkä area, one of their most important winter grazing lands.

“The Committee is unable to conclude that the logging of 92 hectares, in these circumstances, amounts to a failure on the part of the State party to properly protect the authors’ right to enjoy Sami culture, in violation of article 27 of the Covenant.” (para. 7.6)

Kalevi Paadar et al. v. Finland

UN Doc.: CCPR/C/110/D/2102/2011

Communication number: 2102/2011

Author: Kalevi Paadar, Eero Paadar and his family, Veijo Paadar, and Kari Alatorvinen and his family

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Session No: 110

Country: Finland

Date of the decision: 26 Mar 2014

The authors claimed that the government's decision to force the slaughter of their reindeer violated their right, under Article 27 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, to enjoy their Sami culture in community with others.

They explained that reindeer herding is central to their cultural identity and way of life, and that losing their herds would make it impossible for them and their families to continue their traditional livelihood. They also argued that the authorities failed to consider the protection of Sami culture, as required by both the Finnish Constitution and Article 27 of the Covenant.

“In the absence of information in that respect, the Committee is not in a position to conclude, given the limited evidence before it, that the impact of the Ivalo cooperative's reindeer reduction methods upon the authors was such as to amount to a denial of the authors' rights under articles 26 and 27. Despite this conclusion, the Committee deems it important to recall that the State party must bear in mind, when taking steps affecting rights under article 27, that although different activities in themselves may not constitute a violation of this article, such activities, taken together, may erode the rights of Sami people to enjoy their own culture.” (para. 7.7)

**Committee on
Economic, Social
and Cultural
Rights**

(CESCR)

Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR)

The United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) is a group of independent experts that monitors how countries put into practice the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR).

This caselaw guide concerns the application of Article 15(1) of the ICESCR that states that:

“1. The States Parties to the present Covenant recognize the right of everyone:

(a) To take part in cultural life.”

(...)

J.T.et al. v. Finland

UN Doc.: E/C.12/76/D/251/2022

Communication number: 251/2022 and 289/2022

Author: J.T., J.P.V., P-M.V., P-A.L., P-T.J., O.A.V., M-L.V.,
N-M.V., L-T.V., J-O.J., N-A.L., Á-M.L., M.L., M.L., J-T.L., V.T.
and N-M.V.

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Country: Finland

Date of the decision: 27 September 2024

The authors, members of a Sámi community, claimed that the State violated their rights by granting permits for mineral exploration and setting aside a reservation area on their traditional lands without their free, prior, and informed consent.

They explained that these projects, combined with the impacts of climate change, wind farms, military activities, and mass tourism, are threatening the conditions needed for reindeer herding, a key part of their culture and livelihood. This situation, they argued, endangers their ability to pass on their traditional way of life to future generations.

They emphasized that for Indigenous Peoples, the right to maintain and transmit their traditional livelihoods, like reindeer herding, is a central part of both their culture and their economic and social rights.

J.T.et al. v. Finland

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee considers that the issue before it is to determine whether the granting, despite the authors’ consistent opposition and in the absence of an impact assessment, of an exploration permit (...) and the granting of a reservation (...) in respect of areas on their traditional territory without obtaining their free, prior and informed consent, in the context of ongoing climate change and the cumulative effect of other interferences with reindeer herding, constitute a violation of the authors’ right to take part in the cultural life of their community (art. 15 (1) (a)), read alone and in conjunction with articles 1, 2 (2) and 11 of the Covenant.” (para. 12.5)

“The Committee notes that the recognition of Indigenous Peoples’ right to land as an indispensable part of their right to take part in cultural life is in line with international human rights jurisprudence in this area.”
(para. 14.3)

J.T.et al. v. Finland

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee, therefore, is of the view that, in the context of Indigenous Peoples, article 15 (1) (a), read in conjunction with articles 1 and 11, of the Covenant entails the right of Indigenous Peoples to the lands, territories and resources that they have traditionally owned, occupied or otherwise used or acquired and requires States parties to take measures to recognize and protect the rights of Indigenous Peoples to own, develop, control and use their communal lands, territories and resources. It follows that States parties must ensure the effective participation of Indigenous Peoples in decision-making processes that may affect their way of life, in particular their right to land, based on the principle of their free, prior and informed consent, so as not to endanger the very survival of the community and its members, as enshrined in article 32 (2) of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples and reaffirmed in the Committee’s general comments.”
(para. 14.5)

J.T.et al. v. Finland

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee observes that the State party’s failure to give legal recognition to the rights of Indigenous Peoples in respect of their traditional lands, which are the basis for their livelihood and income, has led to a situation in which the Sami are not entitled to compensation when their traditional lands are made the site of mineral exploration (...) and in which they are not recognized as an interested party in the granting of a reservation (...), which has the effect of nullifying the recognition of the rights of Indigenous Peoples to their traditional territories and natural resources and their enjoyment or exercise of those rights. The Committee, therefore, considers that the State party has not demonstrated how, in the processes of granting the permit and the reservation under the Mining Act, the authors’ rights under article 15(1)(a), read in conjunction with article 2(2), of the Covenant were adequately taken into account.” (para. 14.11)

**Committee on
the Rights of the
Child**

(CRC)

Committee on the Rights of the Child (CRC)

The Committee on the Rights of the Child (CRC) is a group of 18 independent experts that monitors how countries put into practice the Convention on the Rights of the Child. It also oversees the implementation of the Optional Protocols to the Convention.

This caselaw guide concerns the application of Article 30 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child:

“In those States in which ethnic, religious or linguistic minorities or persons of indigenous origin exist, a child belonging to such a minority or who is indigenous shall not be denied the right, in community with other members of his or her group, to enjoy his or her own culture, to profess and practise his or her own religion, or to use his or her own language.”

M.E.V. et al. v. Finland

UN Doc.: E/C.12/76/D/251/2022

Communication number: 251/2022 and 289/2022

Author: M.E.V., S.E.V. and B.I.V.

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Country: Finland

Date of the decision: 13 September 2024

The authors, members of a Sámi reindeer herding community, claimed that the government violated several of their rights by allowing a mineral exploration project on their traditional lands.

They argued that the permit was granted without their consent and without an environmental or social impact assessment, even though they had consistently opposed the project. They said this decision threatens the conditions needed to continue reindeer herding, which is at the heart of their culture, identity, and livelihood.

M.E.V. et al. v. Finland

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee on the Rights of the Child also recalls that the integrity and durability of a culture depend on having, in times to come, the conditions for its own ways of life; that cultural rights have an intergenerational aspect that is fundamental to the cultural identity, survival and viability of Indigenous Peoples.” (para. 9.14)

“The Committee also recalls that language, which is the principal mode of transmission of traditional knowledge, is a foundational element of Indigenous cultures and identity. Indigenous children learning and using their languages are key to preserving Indigenous cultures, historical memory and worldview.” (para. 9.15)

“The Committee considers that article 30 of the Convention enshrines the right of Indigenous children to enjoy their traditional territories and that any decision affecting them should be taken with their effective participation..” (para. 9.17)

M.E.V. et al. v. Finland

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee recalls that to ignore the right of Indigenous Peoples to use land and to refrain from taking appropriate measures to ensure respect in practice for their right to give their free, prior and informed consent whenever their rights may be affected by projects carried out on their traditional territories constitutes a form of discrimination, as it results in nullifying or impairing the recognition, enjoyment or exercise by Indigenous Peoples of their rights to their ancestral territories, natural resources and, as a result, their identity. The Committee moreover considers that the discrimination suffered by an Indigenous People also has an impact on children, the preservation of whose cultural identity is crucial, as they represent the continuity of their distinct people.” (para. 9.24)

**Committee on
the Elimination
of Racial
Discrimination
(CERD)**

Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD)

The Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD) is a group of independent experts that monitors how countries implement the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination.

Lars-Anders Ågren et al. v. Sweden

UN Doc.: CERD/C/102/D/54/2013

Communication number: 54/2013

Author: Lars-Anders Ågren et al.

Type of decision: Decision on merits

Country: Sweden

Date of the decision: 18 Nov 2020

The petitioners, members of the Sámi Vapsten reindeer herding community, explained that their culture, language, and way of life are closely tied to reindeer herding, which they have practiced along ancestral migration routes for generations. Their traditional territory covers about 10,000 km² of land, including vital seasonal pasture areas.

They claimed that the government violated their rights by granting three open-pit mining concessions to a private company within their traditional lands—without their consent. These mines and the connected industrial areas would spread dust, destroy lichen pastures (essential for reindeer food), and block migration routes, making reindeer herding impossible.

The community argued that this decision threatens their livelihood, culture, and survival, as much of their land has already been affected by other industrial projects.

Lars-Anders Ågren et al. v. Sweden

The Committee has stated that:

“The Committee observes that, as the *raison d’être* of these principles, the close ties of indigenous peoples to the land must be recognized and understood as the fundamental basis of their cultures, spiritual life, integrity and economic survival. Their ‘relations to the land are not merely a matter of possession and production but a material and spiritual element which they must fully enjoy, even to preserve their cultural legacy and transmit it to future generations’. In this regard, the realization of indigenous peoples’ land rights may also be a prerequisite for the exercise of the right to life, as such, and to ‘prevent their extinction as a people.’” (para. 6.6)

ILO Representations

ILO Representation

The representation procedure is a way for workers' or employers' organizations to report when a country that has ratified an ILO Convention is not respecting it in practice. This process is based on Article 24 of the ILO Constitution.

When a representation is submitted, a tripartite committee (made up of representatives of governments, employers, and workers) can be created to review the case and the government's response. The committee then prepares a report with conclusions and recommendations for the ILO Governing Body.

If the government does not act on these recommendations, the ILO may follow up through the Committee of Experts or, in serious cases, the matter may lead to a formal complaint and a Commission of Inquiry.

Argentina

Río Negro

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Argentina of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Education Workers Union of Río Negro (UNTER), local section affiliated to the Confederation of Education Workers of Argentina (CTERA)

Date: 2008

The representation concerns the Mapuche people in Río Negro, Argentina. It highlights issues related to consultation, political and provincial representation, land rights, and discrimination in carrying out traditional activities. The case underscores the challenges faced by the Mapuche in protecting their culture, lands and way of life.

- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 12 (legal proceedings)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 20 (recruitment and conditions of employment)
- Article 23 (community-based industries)

Argentina

Rio Negro

Selected quotes:

“Representativeness is (...) an essential requirement for the consultation and participation procedures established by the Convention and signifies the right of the different indigenous peoples and communities to participate in these mechanisms through representative institutions resulting from a process that they themselves carry out. For this requirement to be met, it is essential that the authorities ensure that all the organizations resulting from such a process are invited to take part in the consultation and participation procedures, and that the procedures allow all the different views and sensitivities to be expressed.” (para. 76)

“Also taking into account the fact that the issue is one of traditional activities, the Committee recalls that according to Article 23, paragraph 1, of the Convention, Governments shall, with the participation of these people and whenever appropriate, ensure that these activities are strengthened and promoted. Article 2 stipulates that Governments shall have the responsibility for developing, with the participation of the peoples concerned, co-ordinated and systematic action including action promoting the full realization of the social, economic and cultural rights of these peoples with respect for their social and cultural identity, their customs and traditions and their institutions .” (para. 98)

Bolivia

Forestry

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Bolivia of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Bolivian Central of Workers (COB)

Date: 1999

The Confederation of Indigenous Peoples of Bolivia (CIDOB) and other Indigenous and workers' organizations claimed that the Bolivian Government, through the National Forestry Superintendency, violated national and international law by granting forestry concessions overlapping Indigenous lands.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 15 (natural resources)

Bolivia Forestry

Selected quotes:

“In view of the fact that these measures to clear title to the land claimed and expropriations and concessions for mining and petroleum exploitation may directly affect the viability and interests of the indigenous peoples concerned, the Committee recalls that Article 15 of the Convention should be read in conjunction with Articles 6 and 7 of the Convention, and that by ratifying the Convention governments undertake to ensure that the indigenous communities concerned are consulted promptly and adequately on the extent and implications of exploration and exploitation activities, whether these are mining, petroleum or forestry activities.” (para. 38)

“The Committee also observes that the Government states that national legislation contains provisions on procedures for consulting the peoples concerned, as provided by Article 15 of the Convention, with a view to ascertaining whether their interests would be prejudiced before undertaking any programmes for the exploration or exploitation of the natural resources existing on their lands.” (para. 40)

Brazil

Alcântara

Report of the Tripartite Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Brazil of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169)

Date: 2019

The complainants, Quilombola communities in the municipality of Alcântara, Brazil, claimed that the establishment of the Alcântara Launch Centre and the Alcântara Space Centre violated multiple rights under the 169 ILO Convention.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 16 (removal)
- Article 23 (community-based industries)

Brazil Alcântara

Selected quote:

“The Committee wishes to stress the importance of prior consultation as a cornerstone of the Convention and the basis for implementing all the rights enshrined therein. Furthermore, consultation is an essential tool of governance, social dialogue and legal certainty for indigenous peoples, the Government and other stakeholders. The Committee also recalls that the obligation to consult with indigenous peoples contained in the Convention rests with the State, and in this regard underlines the importance of having appropriate consultation mechanisms designed by the Government together with the peoples concerned, and in a manner appropriate to the circumstances.” (para. 57)

Brazil

Forestry

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Brazil of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Union of Engineers of the Federal District (SENGE/DF)

Date: 2009

The SENGE/DF raised concerns about the administration of public forests in Brazil. They claimed that Indigenous peoples were not consulted on a specific legislation about how the law could affect forest management, including the possibility of granting long-term concessions to private companies.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 2 (basic policy and orientation)
- Article 4 (special measures)
- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 13 (lands, territories and the spiritual relationship)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 15 (natural resources)
- Article 33 (administration)

Brazil Alcântara

Selected quote:

“ The Committee draws the Government’s attention to the fact that the consultation process provided for by Article 6 of the Convention includes specific requirements. Not just any consultation process will be in compliance with the Convention. In keeping with paragraph 2 of Article 6, consultation must take place in accordance with procedures that are appropriate to the circumstances, through the indigenous peoples representative institutions, in good faith and with the objective of achieving agreement or consent to the proposed measures. Appropriate procedures are those that create the conditions necessary to reach an agreement or consent concerning the proposed measures. This means that the expression appropriate procedures must be understood in relation to the aims of the consultation. There is no single model of appropriate procedures, which should take into account national circumstances, the circumstances of the indigenous peoples concerned and the nature of the measures which are the object of the consultation process. As regards the consultation process itself, it should take into account the opinions of the various peoples involved in order to facilitate an exchange of information and ensure that the procedure used is considered appropriate by all parties. The Committee emphasizes this point because the validity of the consultative processes provided for by the Convention, as a mechanism to prevent and resolve conflicts, depends on the creation of fruitful mechanisms for dialogue. The consultation laid down in the Convention is therefore not merely a formal requirement but a genuine instrument for participation.” (para. 42)

Brazil Alcântara

Selected quotes:

“According to Article 2(1), Governments shall have the responsibility for developing, with the participation of the peoples concerned, coordinated and systematic action to protect the rights of these peoples and to guarantee respect for their integrity and, according to Article 33(1) and (2), The governmental authority responsible for the matters covered in this Convention shall ensure that agencies or other appropriate mechanisms exist to administer the programmes affecting the peoples concerned.” (para. 43)

“The Committee draws the Government’s attention to the fact that, under Article 15(2) of the Convention, it must consult the indigenous peoples concerned regarding state-owned resources located on the lands defined in Article 13(2) of the Convention, before undertaking or permitting any programmes for the exploration or exploitation of such resources pertaining to their lands that is to say, before licences are granted with a view to ascertaining whether and to what degree their interests would be prejudiced ” (para. 50)

Brazil Alcântara

Selected quotes:

“In the light of the provisions of Article 7(1) of the Convention, the Committee considers that, for timber exploration and exploitation to comply with the Convention, indigenous peoples should be involved in the formulation, implementation and evaluation of plans and programmes likely to affect them directly.” (para. 55)

“Likewise, under the terms of Article 7(3) of the Convention, studies must be carried out, in cooperation with the peoples concerned, to assess the social, spiritual, cultural and environmental impact on them of planned development activities.” (para. 57)

Chile

Consultation

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by the Government of Chile of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the First Inter-Enterprise Trade Union of Mapuche Bakers of Santiago
Date: 2014

The First Inter-Enterprise Trade Union of Mapuche Bakers of Santiago, supported by member organizations of the National Coordinating Office for Indigenous Affairs, submitted a representation regarding the consultation rights of Indigenous peoples in Chile.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 15 (natural resources)
- Article 16 (removal)
- Article 34 (flexibility of application)

Chile Consultation

Selected quotes:

“The Committee observes that Article 6(1)(a) of the Convention does not establish any exceptions with regard to the scope of “legislative and administrative measures”. However, it also observes that Article 7(1) thereof establishes the right of the peoples concerned to decide their own priorities for the process of development as it affects their lives, beliefs, institutions and spiritual well-being and the lands they occupy. It also establishes their right to exercise control, to the extent possible, over their own economic, social and cultural development. Special projects for regions in which those peoples live must be carried out in a manner that promotes improvement in their living and working conditions and their health, and with their participation and cooperation.” (para. 149)

Chile Consultation

Selected quotes:

“Bearing in mind that “a simple information meeting, where indigenous peoples could be heard without having any possibility of influencing decision-making, cannot be considered as complying with the provisions of the Convention”, the Committee understands that the laws and regulations provide that such projects require a further environmental impact study, which offers a procedural opportunity to hold appropriate consultations before a Government authority takes a decision approving or rejecting a given project or activity.” (para. 188)

Colombia

Dam

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Colombia of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Central Unitary Workers' Union (CUT) and the Colombian Medical

Trade Union Association

Date: 2001

The complaint focuses on the construction and operation of the Urrá hydroelectric dam. The unions claimed that the government did not carry out prior consultation with the indigenous communities affected, as required by the Convention, violating their rights to participate in decisions affecting their lands and livelihoods.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 15 (natural resources)

Colombia Dam

Selected quote:

“In the opinion of the Committee, while Article 6 does not require consensus to be obtained in the process of prior consultation, it does provide that the peoples concerned should have the possibility to participate freely at all levels in the formulation, implementation and evaluation of measures and programmes that affect them directly.” (para. 61)

Colombia

U'wa

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Colombia of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Central Unitary Workers' Union (CUT)

Date: 2001

The CUT (Single Confederation of Workers of Colombia) claimed that the Colombian Government violated ILO Convention No. 169 by failing to consult Indigenous peoples before major projects. The examples include a highway through the Cristianía Reservation, a petroleum license affecting the U'wa community, and a decree on prior consultation. The case highlights the need for Indigenous communities to be properly consulted on decisions affecting their lands and rights.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 2 (basic policy and orientation)
- Article 4 (special measures)
- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 15 (natural resources)

Colombia U'wa

Selected quote:

“In the Committee’s view, although Article 6 does not require that consensus be reached in the consultation process, it does envisage that the peoples concerned should have an opportunity to participate freely at all levels in the formulation, application and evaluation of measures and programmes that directly affect them. Moreover, in the Committee’s opinion, Articles 2(1), 2(2)(b), 6, 7 and 15(2) require consultation of the peoples concerned before the finalization of any environmental study and environmental management plan, in stipulating that governments ‘shall establish or maintain procedures through which they shall consult these peoples, with a view to ascertaining whether and to what degree their interests would be prejudiced, before undertaking or permitting any programmes for the exploration or exploitation of such resources pertaining to their lands.’” (para. 78)

Denmark

Greenland

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Denmark of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the National Confederation of Trade Unions of Greenland (Sulinermik Inuussutissarsiuqartut Kattuffiat-SIK) (SIK)

Date: 2001

The SIK alleged that Denmark failed to comply with Article 14(2) of ILO Convention No. 169, which requires governments to identify and protect the lands traditionally occupied by Indigenous peoples.

The complaint relates to the relocation of the population of Uummannaq in the Thule District of North-Western Greenland in May 1953, arguing that the move violated the community's rights to ownership and possession of their traditional lands.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 1 (definitions)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 16 (removal)
- Article 17 (transmission of rights)

Denmark

Greenland

Selected quote:

“The Committee notes that these persons share the same social, economic, cultural and political conditions as the rest of the inhabitants of Greenland (see Article 1(1) of the Convention), conditions which do not distinguish the people of the Uummannaq community from other Greenlanders, but which do distinguish Greenlanders as a group from the inhabitants of Denmark and the Faroe Islands. As concerns Article 1(2) of the Convention, while self-identification is a fundamental criterion for defining the groups to which the Convention shall apply, this relates specifically to self-identification as indigenous or tribal, and not necessarily to a feeling that those concerned are a ‘people’; different from other members of the indigenous or tribal population of the country, which together may form a people. The Committee considers there to be no basis for considering the inhabitants of the Uummannaq community to be a ‘people’; separate and apart from other Greenlanders. This does not necessarily appear relevant to the determination of this representation, however, for there is nothing in the Convention that would indicate that only distinct peoples may make land claims, especially as between different indigenous or tribal groups.” (para. 33)

“The Committee considers that the land traditionally occupied by the Inuit people has been identified and consists of the entire territory of Greenland.” (para. 37)

Ecuador

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Ecuador of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169)

Date: 2021

Shuar Arutam People

The Shuar Arutam People, organized into 47 communities under a Governing Council and General Assembly, claim that the lack of consultation, particularly for the San Carlos-Panantza and Warintza projects, has created mistrust toward the State and threatens their lands, culture, and way of life. Their requests to discuss these projects with national authorities went unanswered, violating their rights to participate in decisions affecting their territory.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 2 (basic policy and orientation)
- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 8 (customs and customary laws)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 15 (natural resources)
- Article 30 (administration)

Ecuador

Shuar Arutam People

Selected quote:

“The Committee wishes to underscore that, under Article 6(2) of the Convention, consultations must be undertaken in good faith and in a form appropriate to the circumstances. This implies full formal consultations, in which both the consulting body and the consulted peoples act in good faith and with the intention of genuine dialogue based on communication, mutual respect and a sincere desire to reach agreement. Consultations must also be informed and conducted in a manner adapted to the circumstances and through representative institutions of indigenous peoples. While the Convention does not impose a model of what a representative institution should be, it is important that it should be the result of a process carried out by the indigenous peoples themselves. An institution may therefore be representative at the national, regional or community level. Indigenous peoples must also be provided with all the necessary information in an accessible language with sufficient time to undertake their internal discussion and decision-making processes in advance. A simple information meeting does not comply with the requirements of the Convention concerning consultations.” (para. 47)

Ecuador

Shuar People

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Ecuador of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Confederación Ecuatoriana de Organizaciones Sindicales Libres (CEOSL)
Date: 2001

The complaint concerns a hydrocarbon exploitation agreement signed on 27 April 1998 between the government and Arco Oriente, Inc. for Block 24, which covers 70% of the territory of the Independent Federation of the Shuar People of Ecuador. The FIPSE members claim that they were never informed or consulted about the agreement, even though it directly affects their lands and rights, violating their entitlement to participate in decisions impacting their traditional territory.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 2 (basic policy and orientation)
- Article 4 (special measures)
- Article 5 (respect for values, practices and institutions)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 13 (lands, territories and the spiritual relationship)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 15 (natural resources)
- Article 17 (transmission of rights)

Ecuador Shuar Arutam People

Selected quote:

“The Committee considers that the concept of consulting the indigenous communities that could be affected by the exploration or exploitation of natural resources includes establishing a genuine dialogue between both parties characterized by communication and understanding, mutual respect, good faith and the sincere wish to reach a common accord. A simple information meeting cannot be considered as complying with the provisions of the Convention. In addition, Article 6 requires that the consultation should occur beforehand, which implies that the communities affected should participate as early as possible in the process, including in the preparation of environmental impact studies. Although in this case the project was established before the Convention came into force in Ecuador, when it did come into force so did the obligation to carry out consultations in respect of any activity affecting the application of the Convention.” (para. 38)

Ecuador

Shuar Arutam People

Selected quote:

“The Committee is of the opinion that the principle of representativity is a vital component of the obligation of consultation. The Committee is aware that it could be difficult in many circumstances to determine who represents any given community. However, if an appropriate consultation process is not developed with the indigenous and tribal institutions or organizations that are truly representative of the communities affected, the resulting consultations will not comply with the requirements of the Convention.” (para. 44)

Guatemala

Mining

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Guatemala of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Federation of Country and City Workers (FTCC)

Date: 2007

The complainant organization alleged that the Government of Guatemala violated ILO Convention No. 169 by granting an exploratory mining licence on 13 December 2004 to Izábal Exploration and Exploitation Mining Corporation (EXMIBAL, now CGN).

The licence covered the land of the indigenous Maya Q'eqchi people in El Estor, Izábal, without conducting prior consultation with the affected communities.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 13 (lands, territories and the spiritual relationship)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 15 (natural resources)

Guatemala

Mining

Selected quotes:

“In accordance with these paragraphs of Article 14 of the Convention, the Committee considers that the Government should endeavour to speed up the processes of the regularization of title to the lands that the indigenous communities traditionally occupy and should ensure not only that their individual rights are guaranteed, but also their collective rights and the various aspects of their relationship with the land. Indeed, the rights to lands that are traditionally occupied as recognized by the Convention do not only relate to ownership and occupation, but also to the survival of indigenous peoples as such and their historical continuity.”
(para. 44)

“The Committee therefore draws the Government’s attention to the fact that, as set out in Article 13, paragraph 2, and Article 15, paragraph 2, of the Convention, and as reaffirmed repeatedly by the supervisory bodies, the Convention does not require indigenous peoples to be in possession of ownership title for the purposes of the consultations envisaged in Article 15, paragraph 2. The consultations referred to in Article 15, paragraph 2, are required in respect of resources owned by the State pertaining to the lands that the peoples concerned occupy or otherwise use, whether or not they hold ownership title to those lands.” (para. 48)

Mexico

Representation alleging non-observance by Mexico of the
Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169),
made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by nine
workers' organizations
Date: 2004

Constitutional Reform

The complainants alleged that Mexico violated Article 6 of ILO Convention No. 169 during the legislative process for the Decree on Constitutional Reform in the Areas of Indigenous Rights and Culture (14 August 2001).

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 6 (consultation)

Mexico Constitutional Reform

Selected quotes:

“In the opinion of the Committee, the appropriate procedure is that which creates favourable conditions for achieving agreement or consent to the proposed measures, independent of the result obtained. That is to say, the expression ‘appropriate measures’; should be understood with reference to the aim of the consultation, namely to achieve agreement or consent. It is not necessary, of course, for agreement or consent to be achieved.” (para. 89)

“In view of the diversity of the indigenous peoples, the Convention does not impose a model of what a representative institution should involve, the important thing is that they should be the result of a process carried out by the indigenous peoples themselves. But it is essential to ensure that the consultations are held with the institutions that are truly representative of the peoples concerned.” (para. 102)

Mexico Constitutional Reform

Cases about the same issue

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Mexico of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Authentic Workers' Front (FAT)

Date: 2004

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Mexico of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Union of Academics of the National Institute of Anthropology and History (SAINAH)

Date: 2004

Report of the committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Mexico of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Union of Workers of the Autonomous University of Mexico (STUNAM) and the Independent Union of Workers of La Jornada (SITRAJOR)

Date: 2004

Mexico

highway construction

Representation alleging non-observance by Mexico of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by nine workers' organizations
Date: 2004

The complainant organization alleged that Mexico violated ILO Convention No. 169 in the construction of the Oaxaca Isthmus of Tehuantepec highway, including a branch road to the Bays of Huatulco.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 13 (lands, territories and the spiritual relationship)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 20 (recruitment and conditions of employment)

Mexico

highway construction

Selected quote:

“The Committee recalls that, in accordance with Article 6, governments shall consult those communities likely to be affected directly, in order in accordance with Article 7 of the Convention, to allow them to participate in their own development and in particular to ensure that ‘studies are carried out, in co-operation with the peoples concerned, to assess the social, spiritual, cultural and environmental impact on them’ (Article 7(3)) and to ‘take measures, in co-operation with the peoples concerned, to protect and preserve the environment’. What needs to be determined, therefore, is whether there was consultation and participation for the development projects as the Convention requires. The Committee observes that the Government does not deny the existence of such an obligation.”
(para. 36)

Mexico

Dam

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Mexico of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Radical Trade Union of Metal and Associated Workers

Date: 1999

The Radical Trade Union alleged that in 1972, the Mexican Government violated the rights of the indigenous Chinantec community of San Lucas Ojitlán, Oaxaca, by constructing the “Cerro del Oro” dam on the Papaloapan River.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 5 (respect for values, practices and institutions)
- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 13 (lands, territories and the spiritual relationship)
- Article 16 (removal)

Mexico Dam

Selected quote:

“The Committee recalls that according to Article 12(2) of Convention No. 107, which was in force at the time of the relocation, and Article 16(4) of Convention No. 169, when a return to their lands is not possible, indigenous and tribal peoples shall be provided in all possible cases with lands of quality at least equal to that of the lands previously occupied by them, suitable to provide for their present needs and future development.” (para. 40)

Mexico

San Andrés

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Mexico of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Trade Union Delegation, D-III-57, section XI of the National Trade Union of Education Workers (SNTE), Radio Education
Date: 1998

The Union of Huichol Indigenous Communities of Jalisco, represented by the Trade Union Delegation D-III-57 of SNTE, alledge violation of land rights by the dipossetion of 22,000 hectares of land in San Andrés Cohamiata.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 14 (ownership and possession)

Mexico

San Andrés

Selected quotes:

“Pursuant to the second sentence of paragraph 1 of Article 14, the Government would be obliged to take measures, in appropriate cases, to safeguard the right of the peoples concerned to use lands not exclusively occupied by them, but to which they have traditionally had access for their subsistence and traditional activities, and this appears to be the situation in this case.” (para. 39)

“Apart from land disputes, the Committee would like to express its concern about the allegations of the organization which made the representation to the effect that the Huicholes seeking the reintegration of the land at issue live in conditions which ‘violate the most elementary individual and collective rights’; since, being a minority compared to the other inhabitants, they have not been recognized in land censuses, with the result that they have no legal rights to the land which they occupy, and it is the majority of inhabitants who decide whether the indigenous inhabitants may plant crops and keep livestock, and their cultural practices are constantly hindered.” (para. 42)

Peru

TUCA

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by the Government of Peru of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the International Trade Union Confederation (ITUC), the Trade Union Confederation of the Americas (TUCA) and the Autonomous Workers' Confederation of Peru (CATP)
Date: 2014

The complainant organizations allege that government policies have caused deep discontent among indigenous peoples, resulting in high levels of conflict and non-recognition of land rights, concessions on traditional land and right to consultation.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 3 (human rights and fundamental freedoms)
- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 13 (lands, territories and the spiritual relationship)
- Article 14 (ownership and possession)
- Article 15 (natural resources)
- Article 16 (removal)

Peru

Dam

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Peru of the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the General Confederation of Workers of Peru (CGTP)

Date: 2012

The General Confederation of Workers of Peru (CGTP) alleges that the Government planned the construction of 15 hydroelectric dams, including three major plants in the Selva Central region, without adequate consultation. The Pakitzapango dam alone would produce three times the output of Peru's largest existing power plant. The project, linked to the Initiative for Integration of Regional Infrastructure in South America (IIRSA) and aimed at exporting energy to Brazil, would involve a 400-kilometre transmission line cutting through the Amazon rainforest, affecting the regions of Ucayali and Madre de Dios.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)

Peru

Land

Report of the Committee set up to examine the representation alleging non-observance by Peru of the Indigenous and Tribal People's Convention, 1989 (No. 169), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the General Confederation of Workers of Peru (CGTP)

Date: 1998

The General Confederation of Workers of Peru (CGTP) alleges that Act No. 26845 (1997), which establishes land titling procedures for peasant farming communities in Peru's coastal region, violates the ILO Convention 169.

Articles discussed in the Representation:

- Article 6 (consultation)
- Article 7 (participation, development and the environment)
- Article 16 (removal)

Peru

Land

Selected quote:

“The Committee considers that it is not for the Governing Body to determine whether individual or collective ownership is most appropriate for indigenous or tribal peoples in a given situation. The Convention recalls the special importance of the relationship of indigenous peoples with the lands or territories, and in particular the collective aspects of this relationship. The Committee notes further, from its experience acquired in the application of the Convention and its predecessor, that the loss of communal land often damages the cohesion and viability of the people concerned. This is why, in the preparatory work for the Convention, many delegates took the position that lands owned by indigenous persons, and especially communal lands, should be inalienable. In a closed decision, the Conference Committee decided that Article 17 should continue the line of reasoning pursued in other parts of the Convention, according to which indigenous and tribal peoples shall decide their own priorities for the process of development (Article 7) and that they should be consulted through their representative institutions whenever consideration is being given to legislative or administrative measures which may affect them directly (Article 6).” (para. 30)

Index

Article 1

1. This Convention applies to:

(a) tribal peoples in independent countries whose social, cultural and economic conditions distinguish them from other sections of the national community, and whose status is regulated wholly or partially by their own customs or traditions or by special laws or regulations;

(b) peoples in independent countries who are regarded as indigenous on account of their descent from the populations which inhabited the country, or a geographical region to which the country belongs, at the time of conquest or colonisation or the establishment of present state boundaries and who, irrespective of their legal status, retain some or all of their own social, economic, cultural and political institutions.

2. Self-identification as indigenous or tribal shall be regarded as a fundamental criterion for determining the groups to which the provisions of this Convention apply.

3. The use of the term peoples in this Convention shall not be construed as having any implications as regards the rights which may attach to the term under international law.

Case

**Danmark
(Greenland)**

Index

Article 2

1. Governments shall have the responsibility for developing, with the participation of the peoples concerned, co-ordinated and systematic action to protect the rights of these peoples and to guarantee respect for their integrity.

2. Such action shall include measures for:

(a) ensuring that members of these peoples benefit on an equal footing from the rights and opportunities which national laws and regulations grant to other members of the population;

(b) promoting the full realisation of the social, economic and cultural rights of these peoples with respect for their social and cultural identity, their customs and traditions and their institutions;

(c) assisting the members of the peoples concerned to eliminate socio-economic gaps that may exist between indigenous and other members of the national community, in a manner compatible with their aspirations and ways of life.

Cases

Brazil
(Forestry)

Colombia
(U'wa)

Ecuador
(Shuar Arutam)

Ecuador
(Shuar)

Index

Article 3

1. Indigenous and tribal peoples shall enjoy the full measure of human rights and fundamental freedoms without hindrance or discrimination. The provisions of the Convention shall be applied without discrimination to male and female members of these peoples.

2. No form of force or coercion shall be used in violation of the human rights and fundamental freedoms of the peoples concerned, including the rights contained in this Convention.

Case

**Peru
(TUCA)**

Article 4

1. Special measures shall be adopted as appropriate for safeguarding the persons, institutions, property, labour, cultures and environment of the peoples concerned.

2. Such special measures shall not be contrary to the freely-expressed wishes of the peoples concerned.

3. Enjoyment of the general rights of citizenship, without discrimination, shall not be prejudiced in any way by such special measures.

Cases

**Brazil
(Forestry)**

**Colombia
(U'wa)**

**Ecuador
(Shuar)**

Index

Article 5

In applying the provisions of this Convention:

- (a) the social, cultural, religious and spiritual values and practices of these peoples shall be recognised and protected, and due account shall be taken of the nature of the problems which face them both as groups and as individuals;
- (b) the integrity of the values, practices and institutions of these peoples shall be respected;
- (c) policies aimed at mitigating the difficulties experienced by these peoples in facing new conditions of life and work shall be adopted, with the participation and co-operation of the peoples affected.

Cases

**Ecuador
(Shuar)**

**Mexico
(Dam)**

Index

Article 6

1. In applying the provisions of this Convention, governments shall:
 - (a) consult the peoples concerned, through appropriate procedures and in particular through their representative institutions, whenever consideration is being given to legislative or administrative measures which may affect them directly;
 - (b) establish means by which these peoples can freely participate, to at least the same extent as other sectors of the population, at all levels of decision-making in elective institutions and administrative and other bodies responsible for policies and programmes which concern them;
 - (c) establish means for the full development of these peoples' own institutions and initiatives, and in appropriate cases provide the resources necessary for this purpose.
2. The consultations carried out in application of this Convention shall be undertaken, in good faith and in a form appropriate to the circumstances, with the objective of achieving agreement or consent to the proposed measures.

Cases

**Argentina,
Río Negro**

**Bolivia,
Forestry**

**Brazil,
Alcântara**

**Brazil,
Forestry**

**Chile,
Consultation**

**Colombia,
Dam**

**Colombia,
U'wa**

**Ecuador,
Shuar Arutam**

**Guatemala,
Mining**

**Mexico,
Constitutional**

**Mexico,
highway**

**Mexico,
Dam**

**Peru,
Land**

**Peru,
TUCA**

Index

Article 7

1. The peoples concerned shall have the right to decide their own priorities for the process of development as it affects their lives, beliefs, institutions and spiritual well-being and the lands they occupy or otherwise use, and to exercise control, to the extent possible, over their own economic, social and cultural development. In addition, they shall participate in the formulation, implementation and evaluation of plans and programmes for national and regional development which may affect them directly.

2. The improvement of the conditions of life and work and levels of health and education of the peoples concerned, with their participation and co-operation, shall be a matter of priority in plans for the overall economic development of areas they inhabit. Special projects for development of the areas in question shall also be so designed as to promote such improvement.

3. Governments shall ensure that, whenever appropriate, studies are carried out, in co-operation with the peoples concerned, to assess the social, spiritual, cultural and environmental impact on them of planned development activities. The results of these studies shall be considered as fundamental criteria for the implementation of these activities.

4. Governments shall take measures, in co-operation with the peoples concerned, to protect and preserve the environment of the territories they inhabit.

Cases

**Bolivia,
Forestry**

**Brazil,
Alcântara**

**Brazil,
Forestry**

**Colombia,
Dam**

**Chile,
Consultation**

**Colombia,
U'wa**

**Ecuador,
Shuar Arutam**

**Ecuador,
Shuar**

**Guatemala,
Mining**

**Mexico,
highway**

**Mexico,
Dam**

**Peru,
Dam**

**Peru,
Land**

Index

Article 8

1. In applying national laws and regulations to the peoples concerned, due regard shall be had to their customs or customary laws.
2. These peoples shall have the right to retain their own customs and institutions, where these are not incompatible with fundamental rights defined by the national legal system and with internationally recognised human rights. Procedures shall be established, whenever necessary, to resolve conflicts which may arise in the application of this principle.
3. The application of paragraphs 1 and 2 of this Article shall not prevent members of these peoples from exercising the rights granted to all citizens and from assuming the corresponding duties.

Case

**Ecuador,
Shuar Arutam**

Index

Article 12

The peoples concerned shall be safeguarded against the abuse of their rights and shall be able to take legal proceedings, either individually or through their representative bodies, for the effective protection of these rights. Measures shall be taken to ensure that members of these peoples can understand and be understood in legal proceedings, where necessary through the provision of interpretation or by other effective means.

Case

**Argentina, Rio
Negro**

Index

Article 13

1. In applying the provisions of this Part of the Convention governments shall respect the special importance for the cultures and spiritual values of the peoples concerned of their relationship with the lands or territories, or both as applicable, which they occupy or otherwise use, and in particular the collective aspects of this relationship.
2. The use of the term lands in Articles 15 and 16 shall include the concept of territories, which covers the total environment of the areas which the peoples concerned occupy or otherwise use.

Cases

**Brazil,
Forestry**

**Ecuador,
Shuar**

**Guatemala,
Mining**

**Mexico,
highway**

**Mexico,
Dam**

**Peru,
TUCA**

Index

Article 14

1. The rights of ownership and possession of the peoples concerned over the lands which they traditionally occupy shall be recognised. In addition, measures shall be taken in appropriate cases to safeguard the right of the peoples concerned to use lands not exclusively occupied by them, but to which they have traditionally had access for their subsistence and traditional activities. Particular attention shall be paid to the situation of nomadic peoples and shifting cultivators in this respect.
2. Governments shall take steps as necessary to identify the lands which the peoples concerned traditionally occupy, and to guarantee effective protection of their rights of ownership and possession.
3. Adequate procedures shall be established within the national legal system to resolve land claims by the peoples concerned.

Cases

Argentina, Rio Negro

Brazil, Alcântara

Brazil, Forestry

Danmark, Greenland

Ecuador, Shuar Arutam

Ecuador, Shuar

Guatemala, Mining

Mexico, highway

Mexico, San Andrés

Peru, TUCA

Index

Article 15

1. The rights of the peoples concerned to the natural resources pertaining to their lands shall be specially safeguarded. These rights include the right of these peoples to participate in the use, management and conservation of these resources.
2. In cases in which the State retains the ownership of mineral or sub-surface resources or rights to other resources pertaining to lands, governments shall establish or maintain procedures through which they shall consult these peoples, with a view to ascertaining whether and to what degree their interests would be prejudiced, before undertaking or permitting any programmes for the exploration or exploitation of such resources pertaining to their lands. The peoples concerned shall wherever possible participate in the benefits of such activities, and shall receive fair compensation for any damages which they may sustain as a result of such activities.
3. Adequate procedures shall be established within the national legal system to resolve land claims by the peoples concerned.

Cases

**Bolivia,
Forestry**

**Brazil,
Forestry**

**Chile,
Consultation** **Colombia,
Dam**

**Colombia,
U'wa**

**Ecuador,
Shuar Arutam**

**Ecuador,
Shuar**

**Peru,
TUCA**

**Guatemala,
Mining**

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Article 16

1. Subject to the following paragraphs of this Article, the peoples concerned shall not be removed from the lands which they occupy.
2. Where the relocation of these peoples is considered necessary as an exceptional measure, such relocation shall take place only with their free and informed consent. Where their consent cannot be obtained, such relocation shall take place only following appropriate procedures established by national laws and regulations, including public inquiries where appropriate, which provide the opportunity for effective representation of the peoples concerned.
3. Whenever possible, these peoples shall have the right to return to their traditional lands, as soon as the grounds for relocation cease to exist.
4. When such return is not possible, as determined by agreement or, in the absence of such agreement, through appropriate procedures, these peoples shall be provided in all possible cases with lands of quality and legal status at least equal to that of the lands previously occupied by them, suitable to provide for their present needs and future development. Where the peoples concerned express a preference for compensation in money or in kind, they shall be so compensated under appropriate guarantees.
5. Persons thus relocated shall be fully compensated for any resulting loss or injury.

Cases

**Brazil,
Alcântara**

**Chile,
Consultation**

**Danmark,
Greenland**

**Mexico,
Dam**

**Peru,
TUCA**

**Peru,
Land**

Index

Article 17

1. Procedures established by the peoples concerned for the transmission of land rights among members of these peoples shall be respected.
2. The peoples concerned shall be consulted whenever consideration is being given to their capacity to alienate their lands or otherwise transmit their rights outside their own community.
3. Persons not belonging to these peoples shall be prevented from taking advantage of their customs or of lack of understanding of the laws on the part of their members to secure the ownership, possession or use of land belonging to them.

Cases

**Danmark,
Greenland**

**Ecuador,
Shuar**

Index

Article 20

1. Governments shall, within the framework of national laws and regulations, and in co-operation with the peoples concerned, adopt special measures to ensure the effective protection with regard to recruitment and conditions of employment of workers belonging to these peoples, to the extent that they are not effectively protected by laws applicable to workers in general.
2. Governments shall do everything possible to prevent any discrimination between workers belonging to the peoples concerned and other workers, in particular as regards:
 - (a) admission to employment, including skilled employment, as well as measures for promotion and advancement;
 - (b) equal remuneration for work of equal value;
 - (c) medical and social assistance, occupational safety and health, all social security benefits and any other occupationally related benefits, and housing;
 - (d) the right of association and freedom for all lawful trade union activities, and the right to conclude collective agreements with employers or employers' organisations.
3. The measures taken shall include measures to ensure:
 - (a) that workers belonging to the peoples concerned, including seasonal, casual and migrant workers in agricultural and other employment, as well as those employed by labour contractors, enjoy the protection afforded by national law and practice to other such workers in the same sectors, and that they are fully informed of their rights under labour legislation and of the means of redress available to them;
 - (b) that workers belonging to these peoples are not subjected to working conditions hazardous to their health, in particular through exposure to pesticides or other toxic substances;
 - (c) that workers belonging to these peoples are not subjected to coercive recruitment systems, including bonded labour and other forms of debt servitude;
 - (d) that workers belonging to these peoples enjoy equal opportunities and equal treatment in employment for men and women, and protection from sexual harassment.
4. Particular attention shall be paid to the establishment of adequate labour inspection services in areas where workers belonging to the peoples concerned undertake wage employment, in order to ensure compliance with the provisions of this Part of this Convention.

Cases

**Argentina, Rio
Negro**

**Mexico,
highway**

Index

Article 23

1. Handicrafts, rural and community-based industries, and subsistence economy and traditional activities of the peoples concerned, such as hunting, fishing, trapping and gathering, shall be recognised as important factors in the maintenance of their cultures and in their economic self-reliance and development. Governments shall, with the participation of these people and whenever appropriate, ensure that these activities are strengthened and promoted.

2. Upon the request of the peoples concerned, appropriate technical and financial assistance shall be provided wherever possible, taking into account the traditional technologies and cultural characteristics of these peoples, as well as the importance of sustainable and equitable development.

Cases

**Argentina, Rio
Negro**

**Brazil,
Alcântara**

Index

Article 30

1. Governments shall adopt measures appropriate to the traditions and cultures of the peoples concerned, to make known to them their rights and duties, especially in regard to labour, economic opportunities, education and health matters, social welfare and their rights deriving from this Convention.
2. If necessary, this shall be done by means of written translations and through the use of mass communications in the languages of these peoples.

Case

Ecuador, Shuar Arutam

Article 33

1. The governmental authority responsible for the matters covered in this Convention shall ensure that agencies or other appropriate mechanisms exist to administer the programmes affecting the peoples concerned, and shall ensure that they have the means necessary for the proper fulfilment of the functions assigned to them.
2. These programmes shall include:
 - (a) the planning, co-ordination, execution and evaluation, in co-operation with the peoples concerned, of the measures provided for in this Convention;
 - (b) the proposing of legislative and other measures to the competent authorities and supervision of the application of the measures taken, in co-operation with the peoples concerned.

Case

“Brazil, Forestry”

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